

Income Smoothing on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Income Smoothing using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Income Smoothing" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Income Smoothing based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 38 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around Income Smoothing, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Income Smoothing; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

The company uses profits to develop its business and provide maximum service to consumers in order to compete with other similar companies. One way to manage company profits is by practicing income smoothing. The purpose of this practice is to prove that the company has little risk and can predict future profit reports. This will increase the impression of good management for parties outside the company.

The implementation of income smoothing in sharia financial institutions is based on Fatwa No. 87/DSN-MUI/XII/2012 concerning Income Smoothing Methods (Income Smoothing) for Third Party Funds which was stipulated on December 21 2012. This fatwa is a reference for sharia financial institutions so that they can carry out profit smoothing practices without violating the rights of customers as investors. Thus, sharia financial institutions can carry out operations in accordance with rules that comply with sharia principles. Implementing income smoothing in Islamic and conventional financial institutions can provide benefits for both parties, namely being able to manage profits well and provide constant profit sharing and minimize losses that may occur.

Scientific publications regarding income smoothing increase every year. In fact, in 2019, there were 42 studies on income smoothing. This proves that the development of research around income smoothing is of great interest to researchers.

Cahyaningrat et al. (2016) raised the topic of income smoothing in their article. This research discusses several variables that are thought to influence income smoothing, such as return on assets, net profit margin, debt-to-asset ratio, and income taxes. The companies studied in this article are banking companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the 2014-2016 period. Of these four variables, the research results show that not all of them have a significant effect on income smoothing.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around Income Smoothing using library research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding Income Smoothing, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around Income Smoothing, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Profit smoothing or income smoothing is an action taken to make the company's financial reports related to profits so that they have low fluctuations, so that the company's financial reports will appear constant by taking into account normal growth rates. The scope of this practice is an effort to reduce total reported profits if profits are higher than normal profits, as well as efforts to increase total reported profits if profits are lower than normal profits.

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In

bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library studies (library research). The object of the research is Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Income Smoothing. which comes from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Income Smoothing " and " Profit Smoothing " for the entire year (20 09 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the

number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for scientific publications on Income Smoothing in Islamic financial institutions from 2009 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last 6 years. Found 36 published article titles sourced from accredited national journals. In 2017, there were 8 published articles. So, on average there are more than 2 scientific publication articles about Income Smoothing every year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data about Income Smoothing by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2009	1	2017	8
2011	1	2018	4
2013	2	2019	6
2014	2	2020	4
2015	2	2021	2
2016	2	2022	2
Total 36			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, it is found that the Journal of Accounting and Investment, Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University, and the Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Financial, Bandung State Polytechnic are the affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles on Income Smoothing in sharia financial institutions, each with 2 articles.

Table 2. Institutions and journals that publish scientific publications about Income Smoothing

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publication
Journal of Accounting and Investment (Muhammadiyah University Yogyakarta), Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Financial (Bandung State Polytechnic)	2
Aksara Public (Edutech Consultant), Accountotechnology (Buddhi Dharma University), Binus Business Review (Bina Nusantara University), Diponegoro Journal of Accounting (Diponegoro University), Equator Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship (Tanjungpura University), Journal of Economic, Management and Accounting (Andi Djemma University), Journal of Economics, Business, & Accountancy	1

Ventura (STIE Perbanas Surabaya), Journal of Islamic Finance and Accounting (IAIN Surakarta), AKUNESA Accounting Journal (Surabaya State University), Journal of Accounting and Information Technology Systems (Slamet University Riyadi), Journal of Management, Economics and Business Applications (STIM Lasharan Makassar), Journal of Business and Management (Surabaya State University), Strategic Business Journal (Diponegoro University), Journal of Islamic Economics and Business (Iqtishodiyah), EMT KITA Journal (Lembaga KITA), Scientific Journal of Accounting and Finance (STIE Putra Bangsa), Scientific Journal of Management Unity (Institute of Business and Informatics Unity), Scientific Journal of Management (Institut Pelita Indonesia Business and Technology), Journal of Management and Accounting Science (Unitri), Journal of Management Science (University Tadulako), Journal of Liability (Satya Negara Indonesia University), Journal of Management and Organization (IPB University), Journal of Neo-Bis (Trunojoyo University of Madura), Journal of Research and Scientific Work of the Research Institute (Trisakti University), Journal of Wira Ekonomi Mikroskil (University Mikroskil), International Journal of Business (Indonesian Technocrat University), Scientific Journal of Accounting (Institut Pelita Indonesia Business and Technology), Accounting Paradigm Journal (Tarumanagara University)

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 3, it can be seen that Bandung State Polytechnic, Diponegoro University, Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University, and Surabaya State University are productive institutions in terms of publishing research articles on Income Smoothing, with each publishing 2 articles.

Researcher productivity around Income Smoothing

Researcher Name	Amount Publication
Rousilita Suhendah and Ansori, Wahidahwati (Pelita Indonesia Business and Technology Institute), Melinda R, Setiawan and Gempita, Pratiwi, Masli (Bandung State Polytechnic), Khasana and Susmitha, Zulaikha (Diponegoro University), Wijayanti, Diyanti and Indarti, Fitria (University Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta), Annah and Musdholifah, Puspitasari (Surabaya State University)	2
Siagian (Bina Nusantara University), Kevin, Jesselyn, Jessica, Erlita, Waruwu, Sitorus (Edutech Consultant), Devi (IAIN Surakarta), Maudinah, Mutasowifin (United Business and Informatics Institute), Kusumaningrostaty, Mutasowifin (IPB University), Nasrifah (Iqtishodiyah), Harianto, Amin, Indah (KITA Institute), Sparta, Trinova (STIE Perbanas Surabaya), Shofiani (STIE Putra Bangsa), Masyithoh (STIM Lasharan Makassar), Auliyah, Zaputri,	1

Yuliana (Trunojoyo University of Madura), Maimanah (Unitri), Aris (Andi Djemma University), Wulandari E, Sutandi (Buddhi Dharma University), Salim (Microskil University), Heriston Sianturi, Wafa Eka Yani Rosita (Satya Negara Indonesia University), Cahyaningrat, Widarno, Harimurti (Slamet Riyadi University), Yanti, Nurdin, Bidin (Tadulako University), Dewi Sukmawati (Tanjungpura University), Sufiyati (Tarumanagara University), Hakim L (Indonesian Technocrat University), Djajanti (Trisakti University)

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for research articles on the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) have been exported to RIS (Research Information System) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer. Here are the results:

Figure 1. Visualization of a network map of research developments around Income Smoothing

Data was processed using VOSViewer 1.6.18 software. co-word map network visualization of the development of research on income smoothing in Sharia Financial Institutions, divided into 10 clusters and 114 topics, are as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 21 topics, namely: BI rate, capital adequacy ratio, CAR, data analysis method, earnings, EBTP, external factors, finance, financing, GCG, good corporate governance, inflation rate, Islamic banking, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial bank, LLP, loan loss provision, NPF, performing financing, tax.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 16 topics, namely: board size, cash holding, company's size, income, income smoothing, income smoothing practice, industrial sector, Jakarta stock exchange, leverage, NPM, influence of company size, profitability.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 12 topics, namely: banking company, company value, debt, DER, dividend payout ratio, DPR, earnings change, equity ratio, net interest margin, NIM, gender moderator variable, winner loser stock.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 11 topics, namely: BEI, Indonesian Stock Exchange, non-performing loans, operating leverage, management, smoothing, income smoothing, listed banking, listed banking companies, profitability, company size.
- Dark purple consists of 10 topics, namely: accrual discretion, bank, bank credit impairment, conventional bank, credit impairment loss, earnings quality, earnings volatility, IAS, procyclicality, PSAK.
- Cluster 6. The blue color consists of 10 topics, namely: banking, financial performance, going public banking company, income smoothing index, LDR, loan, management, NPL, PDN, ROA.
- Cluster 7. The color orange consists of 9 topics, namely: auditor reputation, financial company, firm value, growth company, IDX, Indonesia stock exchange, institutional ownership, company value, significance value.
- Cluster 8. Dark purple consists of 9 topics, namely: banking sector, BEI period, earnings management, funding, Indonesian stock exchange, investors, ownership structure, profit, profitability variables.
- Cluster 9. The light purple color consists of 9 topics, namely: assets, company size, equity, income tax, financial leverage, net profit margin, return, significant influence.
- Cluster 10. The color pink consists of 8 topics, namely: financial sector, fluctuation, IFRS convergence, income smoothing, information asymmetry, management effort, managerial ownership, reported earnings.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 38 Research topics regarding Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

1. The influence of company size, profitability and leverage on income smoothing in the banking industry sector.
2. Analysis of factors influencing income smoothing in non-financial and banking sector companies that went public on the BEI from 2004 to 2008
3. Analysis of factors that influence the practice of income smoothing and its relationship to risk and stock returns in banking sub-sector companies listed on the IDX.
4. Analysis of factors that influence income smoothing actions in banking companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange
5. Analysis of the Influence of Factors on Income Smoothing with Gender as a Moderator Variable in Banking Issuers
6. Factors influencing the practice of income smoothing in banking

7. Analysis of factors influencing the practice of income smoothing in banking sector companies on the IDX in 2009-2013
8. Analysis of the influence of financial performance on income smoothing in open banking companies in Indonesia
9. Analysis of factors that influence income smoothing in banking companies listed on the IDX
10. The influence of IFRS convergence, information asymmetry and managerial ownership on income smoothing in banks listed on the BEI 2010-2014
11. Analysis of income smoothing in Islamic banking in the Gulf countries in the Middle East
12. The influence of internal factors and profit persistence on state-owned bank profit smoothing in Indonesia
13. The effect of leverage on income smoothing and stock returns in banking sector service companies listed on the IDX for the 2010-2015 period
14. The Influence of Net Profit Margin, Return on Assets & Leverage on Income Smoothing and its Impact on Financial Performance in Sharia Commercial Banks in Indonesia
15. The influence of company value, company growth and auditor reputation on income smoothing in the banking sector
16. The Influence of Profitability, Liquidity on Profit Smoothing in Banking Companies Listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange
17. The Influence of Profit Volatility, Income Smoothing and Corporate Governance on the Profit Quality of Islamic and Conventional Banks
18. Income Smoothing Actions in Banking Companies
19. Analysis of factors in granting credit that influence bank profit smoothing
20. Analysis of the Effect of Profitability, Financial Leverage, and Company Size on Income Smoothing (Empirical Study of Financial Services Companies in the Banking Sub Sector on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2013-2017 Period)
21. Analysis of financial ratios towards income smoothing in banking companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2014-2016 period
22. The effect of leverage on income smoothing and stock returns in banking sector services companies listed on the IDX for the period (2010-2015)
23. The influence of profitability, leverage and company size on the practice of income smoothing in banking sub-sector financial companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2015 - 2017 period)
24. The Influence of Company Size, Profitability and Leverage on Profit Smoothing in the Banking Industry Sector
25. Analysis of factors that influence income smoothing in the banking industry and other financial institutions
26. Analysis of the influence of factors that influence the smoothing of profits of banking companies listed on the IDX
27. Analysis of the Influence of Financial Ratios and Good Corporate Governance on Income Smoothing in Sharia Banking in Indonesia (Case Study of Sharia Commercial Banks for the 2012 – 2016 Period)
28. The effect of financial leverage on income smoothing is moderated by firm size in Indonesian banking
29. The influence of company value, Debt to Equity Ratio, and Dividend Payout Ratio on income smoothing in banking companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the 2015-2017 period

30. The Effect of Income Smoothing and Procyclicality Behavior on the Bank Credit Impairment Losses with IAS 39 Adoption in PSAK 55 as a Moderating Variable
31. Analysis of differences in return and risk without IDX banking company income smoothing
32. Internal and External Factors in Sharia Banking that Influence Income Smoothing Actions
33. Factors that influence income smoothing in banking industry companies listed on the IDX
34. The Influence of Company Size and Leverage on Income Smoothing Practices in Sharia Banks
35. The Influence of Internal Factors and External Factors on Profit Smoothing of Indonesian Sharia Commercial Banks for the 2014-2018 Period
36. The Influence of Financial Leverage and Profitability on Profit Smoothing in the IDX Quality 30 Non-Bank Index for the 2015-2019 Period
37. The Effect of Profitability and Company Size on Profit Smoothing in Banking Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange: The Effect of Profitability and Company Size on Income Smoothing in Banking Companies Listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange
38. The influence of ownership structure, company size, profitability, and financial leverage on income smoothing (Empirical Study of Financial and Banking Sector Companies Listed on the IDX for the 2017 to 2019 Period)

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 38 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Income Smoothing in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

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